

The Impact of Halal Branding on Economic Barrier to Entry toward Edamame International Trade

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to establish halal branding in the international trade of edamame products and to describe the company's positioning using halal branding in the international trade of edamame products. This research used qualitative research methods with a phenomenological approach to explore business people's experiences with halal branding on their products. The data analysis findings indicate that the company's halal branding has the potential to outperform competitors in the global market. Through halal branding, it is possible to transform the resulting outcome of differentiated products with a value chain that complies with halal standards. Halal branding can serve as a deterrent to competitors entering international markets. Up to this point, the barriers to market entry have been limited to legal and economic barriers. This article contributes to developing a new theory on trade based on competitive advantage. This paper additionally highlights safety barriers as a type of entry barrier within the context of barriers to entry. Safety barriers to entry in global competition refer to obstacles related to product quality, safety, halal standards, and health, spanning the entire production process to the final delivery to consumers. These barriers serve as a hindrance for new entrants seeking to compete in the international market.

ملخص

هدف هذا المقال إلى ترسيخ مفهوم العلامة التجارية الحلال في التجارة الدولية لمنتجات الإدامامي، بالإضافة إلى تحليل تموضع الشركة في السوق من خلال توظيف العلامة التجارية الحلال ضمن هذا السياق. استخدمت الدراسة منهجية بحث نوعي ذات مقاربة فينومينولوجية لاستكشاف تجارب أصحاب الأعمال فيما يتعلق باستخدام العلامة التجارية الحلال لمنتجاتهم. وتشير نتائج تحليل البيانات إلى أن اعتماد العلامة التجارية الحلال يمنح

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الشركات قدرة تنافسية تفوق نظراءها في الأسواق العالمية، حيث يمكن من خلالها تقديم منتجات متميزة مدعومة بسلسلة قيمة متوافقة مع المعايير الحلال. كما تُسهم العلامة التجارية الحلال في خلق عوائق جديدة أمام دخول المنافسين إلى الأسواق الدولية، والتي كانت حتى وقت قريب مقتصرة على الحواجز القانونية والاقتصادية فقط. وتُقدّم هذه الدراسة مساهمة نظرية من خلال تطوير منظور جديد في نظرية التجارة الدولية يستند إلى الميزة التنافسية، كما تسلط الضوء على نوع جديد من الحواجز، وهي "حواجز السلامة"، باعتبارها أحد أشكال الحواجز أمام دخول الأسواق. وتشير حواجز السلامة في سياق المنافسة العالمية إلى العقبات المتعلقة بجودة المنتج وسلامته وامتناله للمعايير الحلال والصحية، بدءاً من عملية الإنتاج وحتى التسليم النهائي للمستهلك. وتُعدّ هذه الحواجز عاملاً مُقيّداً أمام الشركات الجديدة الساعية لدخول السوق الدولية والمنافسة فيها.

RESUMÉ

Cet article vise à établir une stratégie de marque halal dans le commerce international des produits à base d'edamame et à décrire le positionnement de l'entreprise grâce à cette stratégie dans le commerce international des produits à base d'edamame. Cette étude a utilisé des méthodes de recherche qualitative avec une approche phénoménologique afin d'explorer les expériences des entrepreneurs en matière de stratégie de marque halal pour leurs produits. Les résultats de l'analyse des données indiquent que la stratégie de marque halal de l'entreprise a le potentiel de surpasser ses concurrents sur le marché mondial. Grâce à la certification halal, il est possible de transformer le résultat obtenu à partir de produits différenciés en une chaîne de valeur conforme aux normes halal. La certification halal peut dissuader les concurrents d'entrer sur les marchés internationaux. Jusqu'à présent, les barrières à l'entrée sur le marché se limitaient aux barrières juridiques et économiques. Cet article contribue à l'élaboration d'une nouvelle théorie sur le commerce fondée sur l'avantage concurrentiel. Il met également en évidence les barrières liées à la sécurité comme type de barrière à l'entrée dans le contexte des barrières à l'entrée. Les barrières à l'entrée liées à la sécurité dans la concurrence mondiale désignent les obstacles liés à la qualité des produits, à la sécurité, aux normes halal et à la santé, qui couvrent l'ensemble du processus de production jusqu'à la livraison finale aux consommateurs. Ces barrières constituent un obstacle pour les nouveaux entrants qui cherchent à être compétitifs sur le marché international.

Keywords: halal branding, economy barrier to entry, international trade

JEL Classification: F14, L66, M31, Z12

1. Introduction

The trend of halal labeling has created an oligopoly company. Haque et al. state that a company may be classified as an oligopoly if it has the ability to hinder its rivals from participating in the market (Haque et al., 2024). Qadri identified legal and economic barriers as the main barriers to market entry (Qadri, 2024). Companies' legal obstacles when entering a market are modified following governmental regulations. These regulations pertain to the diverse set of rules implemented within the organization. Quality standardization and product safety regulation is one of the key aspects to consider (G. Khan & Khan, 2019). Halal certification was implemented to standardize quality. This certification is a sign that the products issued by the company are safe, halal, and healthy products (Vanany et al., 2019). Product safety and health are a priority for consumers (G. Khan & Khan, 2019; Mohd Zaid Mustafar & Joni Tamkin, 2013). Producers' main goal is to fulfill consumer-priority products. According to Randeree, this supply leads to an increase in consumer demand. The rise in consumer demand will slow down the economy (Randeree, 2019). According to Selwyn and Leyden, economic barriers are defined by growing economies of scale and reduced production costs. The certification of halal products and the growing economies of scale have created obstacles for competing companies trying to enter the industry (Selwyn & Leyden, 2022).

The position of international trade competition has shifted, moving away from the Ricardian model of comparative advantage to a focus on competitive advantage (Ahiakpor, 2013; Hayajneh et al., 1994). David Ricardo, who emphasizes the importance of a country's natural resources in generating trade benefits, has been superseded by the ideas of Michael E. Porter, which focuses more on innovation and industrial creativity in achieving trade gains (Lambin, 2012; Manzini & Di Serio, 2017). The industry may showcase its innovations and creativity through differentiation. According to Nurrachmi (2018), halal certification has become a significant advantage for competing products in the industry. The presence of halal certification can be a barrier for industries to compete (Nurrachmi, 2018).

We can find this in the international trade of edamame products from Indonesia. Edamame companies always pay attention to consumer

demand conditions in their trading transactions. Companies must fulfill the standards demanded by consumers or export destination countries. Therefore, halal certification did not originate from companies or producers but was instead developed in response to consumer demand. Thus, this research's theoretical gap refutes Jean-Baptise Say's market theory that "supply creates its own demand" (Israelsen & Sanders, 1996). At the same time, the demand for halal-certified edamame products did not come from producers but instead came from consumer demand based on reality.

Furthermore, the study's empirical gap reveals that the analysis of the relationship between the halal labeling trend and company systems tends to focus on linear relationships while ignoring non-linear relationships that affect company control within the industry. The linear relationship's tendency is evident in three types of research. *Firstly*, the correlation between halal certification and the establishment of a brand in a company leads to enhancing consumer loyalty towards the product brand (Ahmadova & Aliyev, 2020; Kurniawati & Savitri, 2019; Nurhayati & Hendar, 2020; Zailani et al., 2019). *Secondly*, the connection between halal and the company's marketing strategy is linked to the internalization of Islamic values (Bashir, 2019; S. Khan et al., 2019). *Thirdly*, the link between halal and its acceptance in the global market is connected to the diverse range of consumers (Abu-alhaija, 2018; Maison et al., 2019). The three trends of research examining the relationship between halal certification and a company's system view halal simply as a label that enhances the product's identity as a brand while overlooking the role of halal certification as a powerful branding tool for companies to succeed in the market. For a long time, the halal certification has been regarded as a way to indicate that products bearing a halal label are permissible and produced in compliance with Islamic law. Existing studies have not addressed the company's use of halal branding as a strong industrial strategy.

This paper addresses the deficiency in understanding the strategic relationship between halal certification and a company by examining how halal branding has contributed to forming an oligopoly company. Following the objective, this study addresses two questions: how does the company carry out the halal branding process? How does the use of halal branding affect the company's strength? These two questions provide direction for the understanding that halal certification is not only a product marker identity but can also be a strategy in the company's competition to

win the market share. Halal certification has allowed companies to become oligopolies and dominate the market.

This paper is based on an argument that companies implementing halal labeling can enhance their image, hygiene, and product safety (Muhamed et al., 2019; Wilson et al., 2010). According to Zailani et al., companies with a positive reputation, good hygiene practices, and high product quality will likely achieve higher sales (Zailani et al., 2018). Consumers will be more loyal to products that are hygienic and safe for their health when making purchases. Companies prefer to standardize quality by giving halal labels because consumers tend to choose hygienic and safe products (Suhartanto et al., 2019). If consumers require products to have halal certification, then companies that meet halal standards will have a competitive advantage in the market and be more likely to dominate it.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Halal Branding

Halal branding refers to a product identity that is strengthened through marketing strategies emphasizing halal values as the core brand. Although the concept of halal branding has been widely discussed by scholars and practitioners, a standardized theory on halal branding has yet to be established. The preference for halal-labeled over non-halal food products has become a lifestyle choice (Masruroh et al., 2021). Abu-alhaija finds that an individual's level of religiosity is significantly associated with their purchasing behavior toward certain commodities (Abu-alhaija, 2018). Halal standards serve as a universal indicator of product quality and living standards (Masruroh, 2020). While halal is commonly associated with material goods, in Islam, it also includes acts and occupations, collectively referred to as *muamalah* (Masruroh, Indah, et al., 2023a). Halal can thus be defined as a quality standard that aligns with Islamic Shariah law and is applied to all activities undertaken by Muslims (Saabar & Ibrahim, 2014).

In the halal branding process, the selection of ingredients—both plant- and animal-based—is essential (Loussaief et al., 2024). To eliminate consumer doubts, producers must evaluate their products and apply for halal certification. In addition to raw materials, other significant elements

include labelling, packaging, and coatings (Riaz & Riaz, 2023). Upon the completion of these steps, halal certification is granted. This certification is issued by the Halal Product Assurance Organizing Agency (BPJPH), confirming the product's compliance with Islamic law. For producers, halal certification adds market credibility; for consumers, it serves multiple purposes: protecting Muslim consumers from non-halal products, ensuring peace of mind, safeguarding spiritual and physical well-being, and offering legal assurance (Riaz et al., 2018).

Halal certification applies not only to domestic products but also to imported goods entering Indonesia (Aminah et al., 2024). Imported products must present halal certification from their country of origin or undergo additional verification by the Indonesian Ulema Council's Assessment Institute for Foods, Drugs, and Cosmetics (LPPOM MUI). Institutions involved in the halal certification process include BPJPH under the Ministry of Religious Affairs, the Food and Drug Supervisory Agency (BPOM), the Fatwa Commission of MUI, and LPPOM MUI under the framework of the Indonesian Halal Council (KHI) (Masruroh, Fadli, et al., 2023).

The explanation of halal underscores that before integrating halal branding into life, one must understand Islam as a comprehensive way of life—*homo Islamicus*, a person who adheres to Islamic teachings. Halal branding is derived from the broader concept of Islamic branding, which is rooted in the theory of Islamic marketing. Although there is no established theory specifically on halal branding, it is often associated with conventional branding theories in marketing management. A product that claims to be halal-branded must be certified and adhere to the standards of a halal supply chain (S. Khan et al., 2019). The decision to position a product as halal-branded influences its market presence. As previously discussed, halal has become a prerequisite for product acceptance (Ruiz-bejarano, 2017). Therefore, for Muslim producers, branding is inseparable from religious values (Garg & Joshi, 2018). Halal branding represents the integration of religious and material elements in everyday life (Rahman et al., 2017).

Halal branding helps identify products that may be considered doubtful or originate from non-Muslim countries (Asnawi et al., 2018). Currently, goods are marketed with various halal logos, depending on national regulations—some even use Arabic script (Azam, 2016). However, for

market access, some halal branding efforts overlook the product's actual supply chain (Mohd Zaid Mustafar & Joni Tamkin, 2013). While halal branding adds market value, it also serves as a tool to promote Islam in daily life (Nurrachmi, 2018).

2.2. Economic Barriers to Entry

According to Porter, barriers to entry are part of the Five Forces Analysis that determine industry competitiveness (Polo & Weber, 2010). Economic barriers to entry are obstacles that hinder or prevent new firms from entering a market (Jelinek & Porter, 1992). These can be natural (inherent to the industry) or artificial (intentionally created) and are designed to protect incumbent firms and reduce competition. There are several key economic barriers to entry in industrial markets. *First*, economies of scale allow established firms to reduce production costs by increasing output, making it difficult for new entrants to compete on price. *Second*, strong distribution networks act as barriers by limiting new entrants' access to the market. *Third*, high initial investment costs create financial constraints for new firms due to capital requirements. Additionally, product differentiation and brand loyalty hinder entry, as consumers tend to stick with familiar and trusted brands (Harvey & Porter, 1988).

Another significant form is legal barriers to entry, often imposed by governments to protect domestic markets. For instance, the United States enforces a 32% reciprocal tariff on products from Indonesia. These legal protections cannot be contested by trading partners, as each country retains sovereign rights over its import regulations. In the context of halal trade, halal certification and labelling serve as entry requirements for products entering Muslim-majority markets. Products without such certifications face entry restrictions. Furthermore, product quality and safety standards have become increasingly stringent in international trade, such as HACCP requirements for exports to Japan or BRC standards for the European Union. These technical and safety-related standards function as safety barriers to entry, particularly relevant in the food industry (Masrurroh et al., 2021; NeioDemirci et al., 2016).

3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Qualitative research was used to explain the connection between halal branding and oligopoly companies, drawing upon both primary and secondary data sources (Chu, PH. and Chang, 2017). We obtained primary data from the PT. Mitratani Dua Tujuh, PT. Gading Mas Indonesia Teguh (GMIT) and Kampung Edamame. All of them were edamame producers from Jember, part of Indonesia. Edamame products have become international, although they were originally Japanese products. Nevertheless, the company remained committed to adhering to the standards required by consumers, expanding its market share to the American and European markets. The edamame product has advantages as it is HACCP certified and holds BRC (British Retail Council) and halal certificates. The local farmers harvested edamame, which was the seed obtained from PT. Mitratani Dua Tujuh or PT. GMIT.

The company's performance has been transformed through implementing halal branding, making the halal label a powerful asset that can give the company a competitive edge and serve as a barrier to entry for competitors. Secondary data includes the background of the company and sales statistics both before and after the implementation of halal branding. The relationship between halal branding and the barrier to entry, which is the company's strength, is analyzed based on primary and secondary data.

The selection of informants employs purposive techniques, which are methods for choosing informants based on specific considerations. This study selected informants based on the following criteria: *firstly*, their understanding of the halal certification process used by edamame producers; *secondly*, their knowledge of the halal production process; and *thirdly*, their comprehension of international trade and market competitiveness in the edamame industry. The chosen participants include operational managers, company halal supervisors, employees, marketing managers, distributors, and consumers. The information obtained from the informants we interviewed constitutes primary data. Information was gathered through interviews regarding the certification process for halal branding, the utilization of halal branding in

international trade, and the potential obstacles that the halal branding process may pose as barriers to entry in international trade. Observation and documentation enhanced the data validity. Before and after the company started using halal branding, we relied on documentation for secondary data regarding company documents related to sales statistics.

Following data collection, three stages of analysis and two data analysis techniques were utilized to conduct the data analysis process. The analysis consists of three stages: (a) data reduction, which involves organizing data more systematically and thematically; (b) data display, which presents research results in tables and graphs (such as interview excerpts); and (c) data verification, which is the concluding stage of data analysis, especially focusing on the data trends. The data passed through these three stages was analyzed using descriptive methods and content analysis. The data description forms the foundation for the contextual interpretation process. Content analysis was conducted using the process outlined by Spradley (Garrido, 2017; Koeswinarno, 2015).

The researchers ensured the validity of the data by employing the source triangulation technique. During the interview, the researchers questioned not one but several other informants who were knowledgeable about halal branding on edamame products. Furthermore, time triangulation was utilized by researchers, who conducted interviews at various points in time. In order to ensure that the interviewees were not only interviewed once, some were even interviewed more than twice, including in the morning and the afternoon. Researchers confirmed the data using not just one but two techniques: observation and documentation. The researchers extended the observation in order to obtain the most recent data. This extra observation involved returning to the research location after processing the data, as there was still uncertainty regarding the validity of the data, particularly concerning halal branding.

4. Empirical Results

The conducted research yields findings on the implementation of halal branding in edamame companies, potentially posing a barrier for competitors. The results are presented as follows.

4.1. The Halal Branding Process by Edamame Company

Consumers are requesting Halal products through their buyers. Consuming halal food has become a popular trend among people. Both the local community and the global community request halal products. Many countries, including Indonesia, are focusing on the production of halal goods and services, as demonstrated by the issuance of Act No. 33 of 2014 regarding the Assurance of Halal Products. The enactment of this law commences on October 17, 2019, which indicates that all MSMEs or producers, particularly those in the food industry, are required to obtain halal certification (information obtained from an interview).

The changing world consumption patterns influenced consumer demand trends. Furthermore, the level of demand is affected by the diversity of each consumer. Some companies recognized this demand trend as a business opportunity, particularly in Indonesia. Japanese companies trust Jember, a regency in Indonesia, to oversee edamame cultivation. While Japan was initially the manager, the people of Jember can now manage it themselves. PT. Mitratani Dua Tujuh and PT. GMIT are the companies trading edamame. The locals of Jember also run Kampung Edamame, a business focused on selling local edamame. PT. GMIT has emerged as a new rival for PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh. Based on the market and economic scale, PT Mitratani Dua Seven is superior to PT GMIT. In addition, PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh is the sole company holding halal certification, as PT GMIT is still in the process of obtaining it. This fact implies that the research focuses on international companies that hold halal certification. it is for PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh.

For this company, which has been committed to producing high-quality food products from the start, to produce products that meet halal standards and certification, PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh in Jember Regency is dedicated to implementing halal branding on its products. The process of halal branding was challenging and involved steps from beginning to end. The edamame produced by PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh is renowned for its

genuine halal status, ensuring the correct labeling and meeting halal standards throughout the production process.

Submitting halal certification is the first step in branding the company's products as halal. The process for halal certification is thorough and includes specific rules. Hence, companies may encounter challenges in adhering to the specified standards. Edamame products hold a halal certificate and undergo the SJH (Halal Assurance Certificate) process. He has completed three SJH audits, receiving a B for the first one due to not participating in the training conducted by LPPOM MUI in Bogor. The second audit received an A grade, and the third audit in 2020 also received an A. The 2008 LPPOM MUI Guidebook stipulates that a new company applying for halal certification will be given the status of SH (halal certificate), but only if it is the second or third submission and export share.

The process for SJH certification is harder than that for SH certification. LPPOM MUI serves the applicants equally and is not selective in their work, which means that even large companies like PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh can still fail certification if their product does not meet the requirements or criteria. For instance, PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh failed to obtain certification for its cake products and many different spices. The issue of meat slaughter certification, though only a cause, has a substantial impact on the HAS process. The guidelines from HAS are based on the halal certification guidelines from LPPOM MUI in partnership with HAS 23000.

Given the existence of JPH (Halal Product Assurance) Law No. 33 of 2014, regulations regarding submitting a halal certificate were changed. Initially, the application could be directly submitted to LPPOM MUI through CEROL, but now it must first go through BPJPH. This change will impact the time it takes to apply for halal certification. There are two essential aspects to be understood in this process: policies and procedures. The fundamental principles established and enforced by LPPOM MUI are known as Halal policies, and these policies guide companies in the management of halal products in order to obtain Halal Certificates. Additionally, the series of steps companies must adhere to to obtain Halal Certificates are referred to as halal procedures. The policy flow and process for applying for halal certification or SJH are as follows:

Figure 1 General Policies & Procedures of Halal Certification

Source: processed

Halal standardization involves branding edamame products as halal. The halal branding is a quality assurance for products and emphasizes the superior quality of edamame products. Halal branding aims to differentiate itself and gain a competitive advantage in the edamame market, both locally and internationally. If they can control the edamame market, then the goal of maximizing profit can be accomplished. The production scale is consistently changing to maximize profits by market penetration. The long-term production scale is always considered at PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh, as there are 4 harvests of edamame. There are occasions when production is halted for machine maintenance purposes. Therefore, adjusting the scale of production can help meet market demands.

Table 1.1: The Analysis of the Halal Value Chain Process

Human Resource Management	Technology and Development	Production	Packaging	Distribution	Service
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Recruiting workers with a contract system. b. Recruiting a healthy, physically strong labor. c. The workforce must be sterile and free from Najis. d. Training every 1-2 months. e. Halal training at the base every 2 years with daily coaching. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Food grade machine b. The machines are clean from Najis. c. The machines are operated for 10 months 2 with months of maintenance. d. Always update seed varieties. e. Plants must have minimal pesticide residues. f. Cold storage machines can have maximum capacity and are clean from unclean objects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Equipment is standardized Halal Assurance. b. Raw materials follow SJH standards. c. Timeliness in the supply of raw materials and manufacturing processes is based on the RKAP, which is prepared annually. d. The production process is simple, and there is always a halal checklist so that it is not contaminated with unclean. e. Export products are treated more specifically. f. New varieties are hatched every 2 years. g. The harvesting process was done manually so that the product was maintained. h. The separation of land between seeding and planting. i. Production process conforming to SOP. Edamame that does not meet the grade is produced as mukimame. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Standardized packaging. b. The packaging conforms to consumer demand by including HACCP, RBC, and halal labels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Special vehicle/transport for edamame and only clean (far from Najis). b. The local trade is cooperation with distributors. c. International trade in cooperation with foreign attaches and trading. d. Promotional techniques that always follow market tastes, especially consumers. e. Follow market trends. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Services are carried out through intensive communication with distributors. b. Preparation of complaints on packaging. c. Carry out repairs and evaluations, especially if there are complaints.

Source: processed

After the process of epoche and checking the reliability of the data, a common thread can be determined regarding the halal branding process that takes place at PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh. The goal of the process is to achieve profit margins. The primary process conducted is the inward logistics process, which involves receiving raw materials that ensure food safety, quality, and halal certification. The equipment used in the edamame production process must meet SJH standards and be food-grade. In order to maintain the production scale, each department creates RKAP for future production planning.

The planting and harvesting processes follow established rules from the operational side, specifically SJH. This process includes ensuring that the product treatment is entirely free from residue. The production process's simplicity conceals the checklist's thoroughness in ensuring the product is free from Najis contamination. The operation was enhanced by external activities, specifically the daily shipment of around 22 containers. SJH has implemented standardized cold storage and food-grade facilities to meet the high demand for frozen edamame storage. Every order is assigned a tracking ID, which allows the products to be tracked from planting to production. If there is a complaint about an edamame product, it is sufficient to check the existing product ID. This product ID has existed since before SJH, but since the implementation of SJH ID, the product has received increased attention and has been better planned. Production is conducted according to SOPs developed based on the standards, such as SJH, HACCP, and BRC.

The marketing model begins with local distributors and extends to overseas distributors through cooperation and participation in international exhibitions. After hosting the HAS exhibition, PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh also took part in exhibitions featuring halal products, both in the domestic market and internationally. This marketing campaign also includes halal transportation, as the containers used for shipping have been inspected to ensure the vehicles are cleaned thoroughly. PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh also benefits from transparency in its production processes for domestic and international distributors. Furthermore, PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh consistently updates its certification and standardization, and it has been demonstrated that the halal certification was initially only a regular one.

The key components, such as inbound logistics, operations, outbound marketing, and sales operations, can function effectively with the support of company infrastructure, human resource management, technology and development, and procurement. The primary and supporting factors have halal value throughout the entire process. The combination of these two components creates the margin. Currently, researchers are unsure of the profit margin obtained. However, based on interviews, the profit obtained by PT Mitratani is only 5%. Therefore, every effort is being made to increase the margin percentage above 5%.

Halal branding on edamame products begins with submissions according to established procedures or regulations. In 2004, PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh applied for halal certification at LPPOM MUI East Java. At that time, government regulations did not stipulate mandatory laws regarding the company's obligation to have halal certification. A research by Edi Krisharyanto et al. stated that the mandatory halal certification was only implemented on October 17, 2019, while the law had been made since 2014, especially JPH Law No. 33 of 2014 (Krisharyanto et al., 2019)

This regulation has implications for how the company conducts when obtaining halal certification, as it is voluntary. Therefore, PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh only applies for LPPOM MUI East Java certification. PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh conducted the halal certification in response to consumer requests. Producers consider consumers their top priority; therefore, they will adhere to any necessary standardization requirements (Al-Hyari et al., 2012). The company's fulfilling consumer demand is necessary to achieve and maintain an expanding market share. This expansion of the market leads to maximizing profits and increasing trade gains. According to Paul R Krugman et al., a company can profit by specializing, primarily when it seeks to compete in international markets (Krugman et al., 1998.)

PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh conducted specialization by applying for Halal Assurance System (SJH) halal certification, which has been required since the enactment of Law No. 33, for halal certification. The initially voluntary obligation for halal certification has now become mandatory, as stated in Law No. 33 of 2014. Before this regulation, the government did not require all companies to obtain halal certification. However, following the implementation of the law, all companies must have halal

certificates. The SJH standardization considers not only the halal status of a product but also its safety. Companies competing in the international market must have SJH.

Halal branding of edamame products is carried out by presenting halal value at every stage and line. This assertion aligns with the differentiation theory stated by Porter, which states that the company will obtain greater profits if it can differentiate or specialize their goods production (Porter & Porter, 2008.). Through his generic theory, Porter believes that differentiation can make a company successful and lower production costs (Weil, 1985) (Polo & Weber, 2010). However, in edamame products, the concept of low cost is not fully used, although it is also being tried.

Quality standardization prioritizes edamame products, giving them an advantage. It can be seen from their certifications, including HACCP, BRC, and SJH. The expenses of offering differentiation are not insignificant, as each process has a halal value. According to Porter's theory of differentiation, every stage must possess value. The analysis results show that each process contributes value to edamame products, making them superior to other products.

The halal value chain is evident in PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh's process of differentiating their edamame products, giving them a competitive advantage over other companies' edamame products. The complete theoretical development of differentiation within the halal value chain has not yet been achieved. The concept of the halal value chain is a valuable theoretical framework in the halal certification process. The halal value chain's achievement is paramount because halal certification encompasses everything from raw materials and production processes to packaging and marketing, not just halal labeling.

The concept of the halal value chain has not yet become a standard theory, but it can be implemented as long as halal logistics requirements are met. The differentiation of edamame products involves more than just the product itself or a single component. Nevertheless, all units are participating in the process of differentiation. Porter's theory of differentiation can be applied to edamame products; however, it requires refinement to incorporate the concept of the halal value chain. Porter's theory of differentiation states that value must be present in every process (Hole et al., 2019; Weil, 1985). Ensuring that each stage of the edamame

production process adheres to halal standards is essential, highlighting the careful attention paid to maintaining its halal value (Hole et al., 2019). Our products are professionally audited and controlled to ensure they are truly halal and follow regulations.

The findings of this study are contrary to Kotler's theory, which suggests that product differentiation is based on the appearance and final product consumers use (Kotler, 2012). According to Kotler's marketing theory, prioritizing end products as a form of differentiation means that he removes the emphasis on the production process of a product (Kotler, 2012). Therefore, a product is considered distinct or original if it is visually appealing, irrespective of the materials or methods used in its production (Kotler & Keller, 2016). According to Porter, to gain a competitive edge or succeed in market competition, a company needs to be able to deliver value from the beginning to the end, from raw materials to post-consumption services for buyers. Differentiation occurs not only in the product but also in every process in the product processing chain. Halal principles incorporate traceability, which means that halal products are tracked from origin to distribution (Masruroh, Indah, et al., 2023b).

4.2. The Impact of Halal Branding on Economics Barrier to Entry

Halal branding in edamame industries uses the traceability principle to give safe food from upstream, the agriculture sector, to downstream, such as restaurants. Not all companies own halal branding in edamame trading. However, for PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh, halal branding is a priority. Therefore, although this research focuses on one company, the company selected is the largest company in the edamame industry in the East Java region. Up to now, PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh has gained Japan's trust as a supplier of edamame. As a result, its halal branding can prevent competitors from international edamame trade. The global market competitors of this product include edamame sourced from China, Taiwan, Thailand, and Vietnam. Chinese edamame products offer lower prices, whereas PT Mitratani's edamame has health benefits (non-cholesterol and gout-free), fresh color, and unique flavor, and is backed by various quality assurance certificates including HACCP, British Retail Certification (BRC), and halal certification.

The primary market for edamame products is Japan, accounting for 70% of sales, while the remaining 30% is exported to various countries including Taiwan, Malaysia, Singapore, Europe, the United States, the Middle East, Dubai, Thailand, Vietnam, Kuwait, Canada, and the Netherlands. There is a barrier to entry in global competition in international trade. The halal certification that edamame companies possess has created a barrier to entry regarding the safety of their products. So, the following model is obtained:

Figure 2: Development of Edamame Product Industry through Halal Branding with Competitive Advantage Analysis

The above flowchart demonstrates that PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh implements halal standardization throughout the entire logistics process, from the beginning to the final stage of delivering goods to meet consumer demand and comply with government regulations regarding halal certification. Internal and external audits are necessary to ensure the high quality of edamame products. The use of halal branding on PT Mitratani's edamame products functions as a differentiating factor from other edamame products, highlighting the advantage of having halal certification throughout the production process. This certification means that halal branding adds value to the product.

Furthermore, the inclusion of halal certification poses a challenge for companies looking to penetrate the edamame market. Based on the evidence, there are legal barriers to entry, economic barriers to entry, and additional safety barriers to entry, all of which are related to the development goals of the SDGs. The main goal of this idea is for the company to win the market and achieve maximum profits.

When examining the international trade procedures for edamame products, there is actually no distinction in export procedures between halal-certified and non-halal-certified foods. The only difference is how transportation and the certificate are handled, which can be used later if the destination country requires the certificate.

Figure 3: The Trading Process of Edamame Products

Source: processed

The figure above provides insight into how each country's specific demands and regulations determine the trade process for edamame products. This finding indicates that edamame is a product created and manufactured with various standardizations to meet consumer demand. The demand will increase once the criteria requested by consumers are met. PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh fulfills halal branding due to the demands from both local and international consumers for standardized halal products. Furthermore, as the number of Muslims continues to grow, the demand for products with halal branding is also increasing among consumers, particularly those of the Muslim faith.

This claim aligns with the neo-classical economic theory supported by Keynes, who stated that "demand creates its own supply" (Grieve, 2016). This assertion implies that edamame production is undertaken to satisfy

consumers' demands and standards. Production occurs when there is a demand from consumers. This theory endorses the idea that consumers have constantly changing tastes, and the market consistently offers what consumers require (Gerrard, 2023). Consumers unconsciously drive every trend in consumer behavior, which the market then capitalizes on by creating industries to satisfy it. Similarly, the same applies to halal products, particularly halal food. The food industry presents halal food products by researching changes in consumer behavior, as they tend to choose products based on their religious beliefs (Vanany et al., 2019; Wahyuni et al., 2019). The government requires producers to meet certain criteria. Food producers must be certified to compete in local and international markets. This certification is a mandatory requirement.

The theory presented by Keynes is the antithesis of the theory given by Jean-Baptiste Say, who provides the theory that "supply creates its own demand" and that the market creates its own consumers (Chambers & Dimson, 2013). If the company does not capture it, even if the market or consumers require it, the consumer's demand will not be met. Producers are responsible for first providing their products and then selling them in the market.

According to Mill, "demand is reciprocal demand," i.e., demand has a reciprocal relationship with demand. If consumers have the role of economic optimizer, they can purchase necessary goods and services. According to classical economics, consumers have desires that are never satisfied. The consumer exchanges his labor for enough income to purchase goods. The income received must be equal in value to the output produced. Therefore, the potential for stockpiling unsold goods can lead to financial losses (Bortis, 2023)

Demand conditions for edamame products indicate that this industry follows the "demand creates its own supply." Consumer demand creates the market for edamame products at PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh. According to the results of interviews, if the edamame processed products such as chocolate, pia, milk, et cetera, are adjusted to consumer demand. PT Mitratani itself, when doing production, always puts the consumer first.

The demand for "halal standardization" is also a part of consumer demand. The presence of "halal" gives PT Mitratani's edamame products a competitive advantage. In this instance, the manufacturers have a

competitive advantage with religious-based products designed to meet market demands. PT Mitratani's competitive advantage allows it to secure a leading position in the market, potentially achieving monopoly status in the international edamame product market. This condition sets PT Mitratani's edamame product apart as a unique offering. In Michael E Porter's 1990 study, it is suggested that differentiation adds value at every value chain stage. Edamame products are distinct items that are produced within a halal value chain.

These findings support the ideas of Ibn Khaldun and Sulaiman (Alswaid & Younes, 2022), Mannan (1970, 1994), Shafi (1979), Tahawi (1992) and Sulaiman (1992), who argue that differentiation arises from producers' learning over time. Product excellence is achieved through the contribution of human labor as the primary factor in production (Lazuardi & Santosa, 2020). The most important resource in production is humans. Therefore, humans need to be aware of the products they create. The motivation for building awareness of halal branding at PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh is to earn profit through production. Nevertheless, it was not constructed with a foundation of religious consciousness among the professionals in the industry. Awareness of halal branding is established through government regulations and consumer demand, making it a means for companies to generate profits.

Research so far that has been talking about consumer awareness in buying halal products, as research by Awan et al. (2015), Afshan Azam (2016), Mohsin Butt et al. (2017), Ali et al. (2018), Garg & Joshi (2018), Jaiyeoba (2019), Kurniawati (2019), Ali Ashraf (2019), Nur Hayati and Hendar (2019), Hosseini and Iranmesh (2019) and many other studies. These studies explore the awareness and concern of the Muslim community towards halal food or food with a halal certificate. Their research discusses consumer awareness of consuming halal food, leading to the creation of a distinct market. When a company enters the Muslim market, it must develop its own strategy, which gives rise to the concept of Islamic branding. This strategy involves producing products with Islamic or Sharia brands.

Incorporating Islamic branding prompts companies to change their business and industrial strategies, as they differ in their theoretical

formation and underlying theoretical philosophies. When it comes to Islamic branding, the religious aspect plays a significant role in the internalization process in marketing. The producers not only need to uphold ethical standards but also internalize the values associated with them. This research focuses on the producer side. The government and buyer requests created awareness and established halal branding at PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh. This finding is consistent with economic rationality in pursuing profits within the company. The company focuses on profit; however, by obtaining halal certification, the business should aim to achieve *Falah* - happiness and prosperity in this world and the hereafter.

When companies use halal branding, they must be aware of the consequences that may arise. Islam regulates the production process according to Islamic values. Even in the absence of halal labeling, it is the obligation of a Muslim to prepare food following the regulations of the Qur'an and Hadith. This assertion aligns with Islamic values in terms of production. At PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh, the halal system has been adapted to conform with laws and government regulations.

These rules bind the edamame production process and system. Institutional issues related to halal certification are being explored because, in implementation, PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh still uses the LPPOM MUI standard, not the Ministry of Religion. This implementation shows that the transfer of authority regarding halal certification, initially voluntary through LPPOM MUI, has become mandatory through BPJPH.

Companies face a problem when it comes to following standardization. The study examines how the state's involvement in halal certification can interfere with trade. The topic of religion, once a private concern, turned into a public matter. Products bearing halal labels are introduced into the public domain to have an impact. Ultimately, halal branding has become more of a business concern for producers than solely religious. Halal branding serves as a means for producers to achieve their goal of maximizing profit by appealing to a specific market.

According to Iranmesh and Hosseini (2019) in their research, religious commitment positively affects consumer purchasing decisions for halal products. This research finding is supported by Nur Hayati and Endar (2019), who state that personal intrinsic religiosity influences consumer awareness of buying food labeled halal.

Segmentation for the halal market is closely linked to increasing the trade volume of a product in Muslim countries. Research on consumer concerns and awareness of halal products has revealed that religious values strongly influence purchasing decisions for products labeled as halal. The company aims to fulfill this demand in order to maintain customer loyalty. When consumers are loyal to a product, the consistency of sales can also be felt.

This study supports Marco Tieman's (2015) opinion that a halal environment is necessary for producing halal products. The company establishes a halal supply chain that starts from planting and ends with the product reaching consumers. Marco Tieman's suggestion that the chain must be in a cluster form is unnecessary. One company is sufficient if all lines are differentiated using a halal value chain. Furthermore, halal branding offers several benefits, such as allowing consumers to familiarize themselves with the product, providing greater opportunities for product differentiation, fostering brand loyalty and repeat purchases, enabling premium pricing, and making product demand less elastic (Tieman & Tieman, 2015). These benefits contribute to the higher trading volume of edamame products. Consumers do not easily recognize the edamame brand without effective branding, contributing to its differentiation. Halal branding is considered an advantage that can lead to a rise in trade volume.

From an industrial perspective, there is no change, but it is necessary to internalize the standards achieved in the practice of edamame production. This internalization will raise awareness of the production system. The industrial changes involve inputting the trace code in each section and being more cautious to prevent product contamination with unclean substances, as indicated in the form of a checklist.

According to a study conducted by Turnois, faith should serve as the foundation for the theory of halal branding in Islamic marketing. Furthermore, the availability of halal products aims to enhance the connection between products and Muslim consumers (Bukhari et al., 2019). Therefore, this study conflicts with the research conducted by Turnois (2015) and Bukhari & Isa (2019), as at PT Mitratani Dua Tujuh, the awareness of conducting halal production is shaped by regulations and influenced by the producer's economic rationale, specifically the goal of maximizing profits.

The halal market or industry is currently expanding, with edamame products playing a role in the halal food market. According to the GIE 2024/2025 report, Indonesia has successfully moved up to the second position in the global halal food development. Therefore, Indonesia needs to be capable of offering halal products throughout the entire supply chain, "farm to fork," from agricultural production to the dining tables of restaurants or customers. The goal is to inspire confidence in the products that consumers consume. This target is intended to help Indonesia achieve its goal of becoming the global hub for halal products by 2024.

This explanation can be described in the halal food industry development model:

Figure 3: Halal Food Industry Development Model

Source: processed

The figure above is transformed into a model designed for the halal food industry. The change that took place in this industry was the implementation of standardization, leading to the requirement for all products and processes in the industry to be certified as halal. The halal industry is concerned not just with labels but also with companies adhering to halal standards. This label indicates that it is not just about making a profit but also discussing the level of religious beliefs of the producers.

5. Conclusion

This study draws two conclusions regarding the influence of halal branding on product development. The integration of halal branding in the global edamame trade can be observed throughout the process of halal branding, international trade procedures involving halal branding, and the sales volume of products using halal branding. This result reveals that halal branding effectively creates product differentiation by emphasizing a halal value chain. Products featuring halal branding may present a barrier to entry for non-halal products, particularly those lacking a safety barrier to entry. The research findings contribute to the theory of barriers to entry in market competition by identifying safety barriers as a theoretical contribution. Therefore, companies with halal certification can effectively compete with their rivals by ensuring product safety and health. In addition, halal branding can help a company expand its market network. The impact is yielding an increase in sales volume, indicating that halal branding ensures the safety and health of the products in the industry. Thus, it can serve as a deterrent for competitors looking to enter the market. The edamame trading industry evidences this.

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